

Leveraging Indian Secularism as a Soft Power in South Asia

Akash Barua

Research Scholar, Department of Political Science, University of Delhi

Abstract

Underdevelopment in South Asia is a multifaceted issue, characterised by various social, economic, and political challenges. The region is largely acknowledged for its diverse cultures and ethnicities, consisting of eight nations. Despite comprising a significant portion of the world's population, and encompassing a rich cultural heritage, the region faces several obstacles to development, such as poverty, lack of access to healthcare, gender inequality, and many others. One of the numerous reasons, that could be attributed to its current state, is the constant social frictions, arising out of the differences among the various ethnic groups. While the region is celebrated as a 'salad bowl' of distinct cultures, this perceived strength has also become one of its major hindrances to social advancement.

The British Raj played a direct political role in shaping the boundaries and identities of the ethnic groups, which contributed to the nation-state model in South Asia. This imposition significantly reshaped regional dynamics, often heightening ethnic and social conflicts. Additionally, its policy of 'divide and rule' exacerbated existing divisions, pitting communities against one another to consolidate control. This legacy of division has continued to influence inter-ethnic relations and national identities in the region, contributing to existing conflicts and tensions. Instead of minimising differences, unlike the European counterpart, the nation-state model failed to promote fraternity within and among nations in this part of the world.

The diversity of the region demands a strong binding force, an effective doctrine, that could unite the different societies, and facilitate greater cooperation among them. The central question that will guide the essence of my paper, is: 'Can secularism be leveraged as a soft power in South Asia? If so, what principles could actualise this endeavour?' For inspiration, the paper will look into the idea of secularism as perceived by the founding fathers of the Indian constitution. If largely adopted, the principles of Indian secularism could play a transformative role in modernising the region. Its principles contain several vital ingredients that are required by modern nation-states for effective governance. The ideals, if pursued, could also become a remedy, if not a permanent solution to many of the social conflicts.

Firstly, the paper will look into the advent of secularism, in the context of its evolution in India and the subcontinent. It will then discuss three of its essential principles and how they could help to resolve the existing social problems in the region; the principles are 1) State Neutrality, 2) Positive State Interventionism, and 3) The Freedom to Profess. The paper will discuss some of the major conflicts in the region, and argue the usefulness of these principles in mitigating them. Finally, it will argue the need to adopt secularism as a 'cultural doctrine', positioning it as a beacon for modernity in South Asia.

Keywords: *Secularism, Indian Secularism, Soft Power, South Asia, Modernity, Social Advancement*